

**NOVEL PV CONVERSION MECHANISMS
IN CRYSTALLINE SILICON FILLED
WITH CONDITIONED AMORPHIZED GRAINS**

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ABSTRACT: Our research reveals a novel mechanism for low-energy generation and multiplication of secondary electrons in silicon nanostructures, specifically triggered by the UV component of the solar spectrum. By harnessing the additional kinetic energy of hot electrons, we introduce a complementary photovoltaic (PV) conversion pathway to surpass the Shockley-Queisser efficiency limit of 30% in silicon solar cells. These experimental findings, along with their theoretical interpretation, were developed within the LEEMONS Project. They directly informed the innovative design and architecture of the hidden tandem demonstrators, which were subsequently fabricated to meet stringent performance requirements.

Keywords: Silicon Solar Cell, High-Efficiency, Interfaces and Nanocomponents, Hot Electrons, Low-energy Secondary Generation and Multiplication.

1 INTRODUCTION

Amorphized grains have been built-in into crystalline silicon lattice by the ion implantation, their controlled amorphization and thermodynamic conditioning. Such an immersion is unfortunately always accompanied by postimplant defects with highly active recombination centers that completely obscures the desired effects of photogeneration.

This work presents the spectacular revelation of a phenomenon triggered by hard UVs in a transformed Si wafer; the secondary generation in highly hostile environment, see Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Built-in amorphized nanograins in unifacial silicon test device with a near-perfectly passivated front face (artist's view).

2 EXPERIMENT

FIG. 2 presents an optical view of built-in nanosystem of amorphized grains while FIGs. 3 and 4 show TEM image of amorphized grain cross section and the positions of the two built-in SEG-Matter nanolayers that are well-visualized on the SIMS fluorine profile; upper, at a depth greater than **19.5 nm** and lower, at a depth greater than **28 nm**.

Significant changes in the spectral response measurement conditions enable insight into the generation-recombination (G-R) balance even in the presence of strong recombination activity at well-defined zones.

Figure 2: A nanosystem featuring 2 μm amorphized grains built-in into a crystalline silicon wafer, visualized by optical microscopy.

Figure 3: TEM image of a cross-section illustrating the geometric structure of buried amorphized grains, the layers from top to bottom: upper crystalline, middle amorphous, and lower crystalline.

It should be emphasized that both defects and the secondary generation centers are localized at the superficial zone of the wafer. FIG. 1 illustrates the defected area, in which are plunged the generation centers that are internal to a Si metamaterial, named SEG-Matter.

Indeed, the precise positions of the two built-in SEG-Matter nanolayers appear in SIMS measurements, as shows the related fluorine profile, see FIG. 4.

The active surface coverage of SEG-Matter is limited to that of amorphized grains.

Figure 4: The positions of the two built-in SEG-Matter nanolayer appear clearly on the SIMS fluorine profile: the upper layer at a depth exceeding 19.5 nm and the lower layer at a depth exceeding 28 nm.

2.1 Experimental Protocol and Strategy

An optimized experimental protocol enables direct visualization of light-induced phenomena in silicon-embedded nanostructures. The protocol for our spectral response measurements is designed to deliberately manipulate the G-R balance to achieve defect saturation.

Spectral response measurements, under steady-state and time-resolved excitation, reveal abundant secondary electron generation, even in the presence of strong internal recombination. This secondary generation, localized at the wafer surface, is made observable through near-perfect electron transport and dynamic control of the G-R balance.

2.2 Methods for Achieving Defect Saturation

Saturation of the near-surface recombination centers can be achieved in two ways:

- (i) By applying a continuous, broad-spectrum white light optical bias to maintain a steady-state population of free carriers that fill the defect states.
- (ii) By increasing the flux of the monochromatic probe beam itself, so that it is intense enough to simultaneously generate collectable free carrier population that is enable to saturate the defects.

2.3 Key Challenges

The main obstacle is isolating the intrinsic optoelectronic activity of SEG-Matter nanostructures, which are integrated into crystalline silicon via ion implantation. The near-surface region, where UV absorption occurs, suffers from high-localized recombination due to surface states and postimplant defect zone, usually masking the useful photogeneration.

2.4 Solution

To observe the specific electronic activity of SEG-Matter under so adverse conditions, it is necessary to suppress or passivate the recombination pathways associated with the postimplant defects localized close to the surface zone.

This is possible to achieve this by employing an **optical bias** technique and different conditions of spectral response measurements.

3 RESULTS

Figure 6 shows the measured spectral response across the entire spectral range, highlighting a distinct feature in the long-wavelength range (800–1100 nm).

Figure 5: The dark-measured spectral response across the full range highlights a specific long-wavelength region (800–1100 nm), where external circuit collection is observed.

Longer-wavelength light penetrates deeper into the wafer, beyond the defect-rich near-surface region, generating a primary population of electron-hole pairs in the "clean" bulk of the semiconductor. Here, recombination from postimplant defects is negligible. However, a second harmful effect persists: the "sink effect," which causes internal recombination of photocarriers generated in the bulk. These carriers can diffuse back toward the defect-laden near-surface region and be annihilated before collection in the external circuit.

This leakage recombination acts as a powerful sink, ensuring that the overall G-R balance remains dominated by near-surface defects. As a result, the photogenerated carrier population is insufficient to overcome this sink, preventing net current collection in the external circuit at middle wavelengths (400–800 nm).

In general, recombination occurs at front-defects or rear-side contacts. Whereas in the wavelength range between 800 and 1100 nm, useful recombination on contacts predominates. Figure 1 illustrates the device structure, showing how the sink effect drives internal carrier recombination within the surface-damaged zone surrounding amorphized grains.

3.1 Spatial differentiation of photogeneration and recombination areas

Spatial segregation of G-R dynamics, both near the surface and in the bulk, as well as near and far from defects, enables targeted investigation of carrier photogeneration in the short-wavelength range (250–400 nm) via efficient carrier collection, as evidenced by short-circuit current measurements.

At UV, photogeneration remains confined to the shallow depth of light penetration. The "sink effect", where bulk-generated carriers diffuse back and recombine at near-surface defects, is absent, since free carrier generation does not occur in the bulk. Instead, the generation-recombination balance and net current collection are governed exclusively by the superficial zone.

3.2 Carrier collection

Carrier collection was first observed in the long-wavelength range (800–1000 nm), as shown in Fig. 6. This phenomenon arises from the spatial localization of absorption sites and the relative proximity of the collecting contacts, enabling effective collection of electron-hole pairs.

Under the established experimental conditions (detailed experimental protocol), efficient carrier collection should be observed in the short-wavelength UV range. Indeed, the high photogeneration rate saturates defect-related recombination centers, while the near-perfect quality of the wafer ensures excellent carrier transport.

3.3 Time-resolved measurements

Time-resolved photogeneration experiments focused on the surface region reveal critical insights. When the photogeneration intensity exceeds a threshold, internal recombination is dynamically suppressed, as shown in FIG. 6.

Figure 6: Dynamic EQE in a highly recombinant environment, the G-R balance. Results show in: upper graph, a shorter 3 nm wavelength spread indicated by thin blue vertical lines. Comparison of curves acquired under two distinct conditions: i) without optical bias (orange) and ii) with optical bias (blue); lower graph, a larger 10 nm wavelength spread of the measurement points. Conditions: concentrated spot, acquisition time 1 sec/pt, average over three measurements per point.

The suppression of the recombination activity allows measurements to track the evolution of free electron populations and precisely locate secondary generation centers under UV excitation.

A wavelength-dependent scan further exposes the interplay between beneficial (contact-mediated) and detrimental (defect-driven) recombination processes.

Slow-scan UV measurements, highlight dynamic shifts in the G-R balance. This approach enables real-time observation of transient free electron populations in nanostructured silicon wafers, capturing their formation, electron transport and decay.

3.4 Abundant secondary generation

The experimental approach created conditions that allowed observation of abundant secondary carrier generation in the short-wavelength range (250–400 nm), even in the presence of highly active recombination centers, by dynamically modulating the G-R balance.

All observed data result from two recombination mechanisms: beneficial recombination at contacts and detrimental recombination at defects.

Surpassing a certain generation intensity threshold indicated complete dynamic suppression of internal recombination.

Moreover, UV illumination enables precise spatial mapping of these secondary generation sites, see FIG. 7.

Figure 7: Collection of hard UV conversion in a silicon test device measured in different conditions.

The thresholds of two direct bandgaps are marked by vertical lines: first (green line) at 3.43 eV (358.6 nm) and second (blue line) at 4.32 eV (284.7 nm). The penetration depth of light into crystalline silicon is shown for comparison.

Three spectral responses are shown: dark curve, usual in the dark; blue curve, usual in the dark but with a stronger incident beam; rose curve, measured with optical bias.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Through our experimental approach, we established conditions to improve the detection of secondary generation, even amidst particularly adverse G-R balances. This measurement methodology will be used as part of LEEMONS project to improve solar cell characterization understanding.

A time-resolved equilibrium between generation and recombination was distinctly evident. Elevated photogeneration, driven by well-integrated secondary generation centers, temporarily neutralizes recombination activity under UV excitation.

All observed data are attributable to two recombination mechanisms: beneficial recombination occurring at contacts and detrimental recombination associated with defects.

References

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